

Assessment of the Challenges and Disparities Circumstances of Tea Garden Workers of Bangladesh

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Abstract

Bangladesh, distinguished for its flourishing tea sector, significantly depends on the labor and efforts of tea workers. The socioeconomic circumstances of these workers in an alternative sociolinguistics context have raised concerns due to their susceptibility to several hurdles and disparities. This article seeks to examine and evaluate the socioeconomic conditions of Bangladeshi tea estate workers, highlighting their living standards, salary levels, access to essential utilities, and general quality of life. The principal aim of this research is to evaluate the income levels and financial stability of tea workers. The study will also analyze the provision of social security benefits, encompassing healthcare, housing, and education, through the lens of Marxist theory. The investigation will examine the working conditions and labor rights of tea workers. The study will examine factors including worker safety, access to potable water and sanitation facilities, and compliance with labor laws and regulations. This research will enhance the current literature on labor and socioeconomic situations within the sociolinguistics context of Bangladesh, offering significant insights for policymakers, industry stakeholders, and groups dedicated to the welfare of tea workers. The study is anticipated to establish a basis for formulating targeted interventions and policy reforms to enhance the well-being and livelihoods of tea workers in Bangladesh.

Keywords: tea sector, tea workers, Workers, socioeconomic circumstances, social security, sociolinguistics context.

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1. Introduction

Bangladesh, with numerous plantations around the country, ranks among the leading tea exporters globally. The predominant workforce in the tea sector consists of women, who face arduous working conditions and extended hours for minimal compensation. Tea workers have been systematically exploited by the industry for decades, despite residing in some of the most isolated corners of the nation. Approximately 150,000 of the nation's lowest-paid workers, specifically tea gardeners, are advocating for a 150 percent rise in their daily income [1].

Tea, Bangladesh's second major export-oriented cash crop, holds considerable significance in cultural heritage, social structure, and the economy. The country has 163 tea estates covering over 49,000 hectares, contributing around 1.37% to the global tea trade [2]. The labor-intensive, agro-based tea business of Bangladesh requires the diligent efforts of laborers throughout the entire production process [3].

The labour and contributions of tea workers are vital to Bangladesh, celebrated for its flourishing tea industry. The socioeconomic circumstances of these workers have elicited concerns due to their susceptibility to several hurdles and injustices. This thesis seeks to analyse and assess the socioeconomic situations of Bangladeshi tea workers, providing insights into their general quality of life, income distribution, and access to vital resources. The cultivation and production of tea have been vital to Bangladesh's economy for numerous years. A substantial segment of the population is engaged in the sector, especially in the northeastern areas where the majority of tea plantations are located. Despite the economic importance of tea production, there has been a lack of thorough research on the welfare and living situations of tea workers, highlighting the need for an in-depth examination of their socioeconomic status [4, 5].

According to the statistics of Bangladesh Tea Board, there are 163 tea estates employ 19,592 casual workers alongside 89,812 registered workers. Among them, 12.1% are adolescents, 44.1% are male, and 43.8% are female. Tea garden workers are collectively deprived of all fundamental human rights, including accommodation, food, clothing, healthcare, and education. Due to significant levels of ignorance, illiteracy, social marginalization, economic hardship, and other issues, they are

compelled to persist in a traditional lifestyle with limited prospects [6, 7]. Certain study indicates that tea workers endure inhumane living and working conditions, along with inadequate access to sanitation and healthcare services. The majority of individuals, including women and children, fail to meet the recommended dietary intake, resulting in a significant deficiency in food and nutrition knowledge and practices [8, 9].

Tea workers constituted the primary community engaged in tea cultivation in Bangladesh, as this occupation was inherited through familial lineage. They are landless, and their families have relied on tea farms for their livelihoods for centuries, lacking alternative work opportunities. Consequently, successive generations became bound to them in tea plantations. The adolescents in tea plantations lack opportunities in other employment sectors and are nearly compelled to enter the tea labour market as unskilled workers. The workers in tea gardens perceive this profession as a challenge to sustain their livelihoods, relying on the tea plantations for sustenance, water, shelter, education, healthcare, and sanitation, rendering them very susceptible to closures [11, 12].

In this context, vulnerability refers to the reduced ability of an individual or community to foresee, manage, withstand, and recuperate from the effects of the low wages of tea workers. This approach has been utilized across several research traditions to evaluate the vulnerability of tea workers' income, aiming to ascertain the overall vulnerability of individual workers in relation to their income threshold. Bangladesh may generate substantial foreign money from tea exports, primarily due to the efforts of tea garden workers. It is regrettable that there is a lack of prioritization in providing facilities for tea garden workers. Their inadequate housing, meagre salaries, extended working hours, and social discrimination deny tea workers and their children of fundamental human necessities and rights, ensuring that they remain trapped in a cycle of generational tea labour [13, 14]. Consequently, evaluating income vulnerability may be crucial for enhancing their livelihoods. Evaluating income vulnerability elucidates how income variability manifests and its sensitivity to associated factors, as well as the role of adaptive capability in coping mechanisms. This study aims to elucidate the income vulnerability of tea workers. The study aims to uncover the elements that may contribute to workers experiencing income vulnerability. The study's findings will assist researchers and

policymakers in making informed decisions to mitigate the income vulnerability of tea workers. It would motivate fresh researchers to investigate this subject [15, 16].

In Bangladesh, tea colony workers of the gardens had a lamentable past characterized by injustice, deprivation, exploitation, and dissatisfaction. They are so completely restricted that they rely exclusively on corporations for sustenance. A study conducted on two tea estates in Chattogram, namely Ramgarh Tea Estate and Kodala Tea Estate, demonstrated the social rejection faced by tea yard workers about healthcare, housing, education, and other matters [17]. They lack autonomy over their lives and services, and they are denied any social status in Bangladesh. Their inadequate compensation, extended working hours, adverse working conditions, and social marginalization deprive them of essential human rights and sites [18, 19]. This condition is critically regarded as a manifestation of the ongoing class struggle from a Marxist viewpoint, which is a fundamental foundation. Their lifestyle is inhumane. They are unable to participate in the proposed land society. The concept of social rejection is relatively novel, resulting in a lack of comprehensive investigation among tea yard workers. Previous research indicates that social rejection is the phenomenon whereby individuals or groups are entirely or partially excluded from fully participating in the society in which they reside [20, 21]. It references Marxism, a socioeconomic and political theory that analyses the impact of the ruling class on the working class and the resultant inequitable distribution of wealth. Individuals who are marginalized are prohibited from accessing employment, credit, loans, housing, land, a basic standard of living, healthcare, health education, cultural practices, familial connections, social interactions, respect, citizenship, legal parity, participatory decision-making, and public resources. Social popularization arises from social exclusion [22]. The less fortunate people of the affluent society are unable to access some social amenities.

This study highlights the importance of the global economic system in sustaining the subjugation of developing nations. The tea business in Bangladesh is frequently included into global supply chains, dominated by multinational corporations. This integration may exacerbate the reliance of tea garden worker on foreign markets and expose them to the fluctuations of global commodity prices. Furthermore, the sociolinguistics circumstances of

the workers hinder their integration into the broader society of our nation. Consequently, individuals experience heightened prejudice both within and beyond the societal framework.

2. Methodology

This study is undertaken in both urban and rural settings of the district, specifically at two tea gardens in Chattogram: Ramgarh Tea Estate and Kodala Tea Garden. This paper utilizes data from both quantitative and qualitative methodologies. Primary data were gathered via a questionnaire administered through face-to-face interviews. The researchers employed purposive sampling to choose two tea gardens in Chattogram: Ramgarh Tea Estate and Kodala Tea Garden. A total of 50 tea garden workers were randomly selected, all of whom have been continually engaged in this occupation across generations. The researchers visited the residences of select respondents, participated in their social gatherings, and studied their household dynamics, living standards, religious practices, dietary habits, cleanliness, sanitary conditions, and the status of their children and other family members. The aim of quantitative measures is to collect data that may be quantified and represented as frequencies, rankings, or percentages. Supplementary sources of quantitative data include questionnaires, self-assessments, and checklists. The closed-ended questions gathered from tea garden workers have been analyzed using quantitative research methods in the subsequent chapter. Additionally, twelve closed-ended questions have been incorporated, presented numerically. Data for the literature review have been gathered from secondary sources, including books, reports, journal articles, publications, newspapers, and online resources.

This study is a qualitative observational research based on interviews. Secondary data were gathered from several sources to facilitate the research by analyzing existing information. This research employs inductive reasoning. Inductive reasoning has yielded fresh insights and theories from the evidence, rather than verifying preexisting hypotheses.

This research can be conducted by numerous experiments, questionnaires, and interviews, utilizing diverse existing data obtained from multiple sources. This research is conducted through interviews with tea workers and the utilization of preexisting data.

The second method is a qualitative inquiry aimed solely at acquiring thoughts regarding the lives of Tea Garden Workers. The subsequent section presents the open-ended questions and interviews acquired through qualitative research methods.

This research employs precise patterns and observations to validate the initial concept. The objective of this research is to analyse the socioeconomic conditions and realities of tea workers. This research is developed through meticulous observation. The research is conducted using the acquired data and aims to elucidate through explanations. Inductive reasoning facilitates the generalization of a subject through observation and data analysis conducted via study. This research is also conducted through empirical evidence and case studies.

This work significantly contributes to the understanding of the socioeconomic conditions, language, and culture of tea garden staff. This research employed both closed and open ended questions to get data from the Tea Garden Workers. The data were taken from two tea gardens in Chattagram, namely Ramgarh Tea Estate and Kodala Tea Garden. Not all individuals reply to the questionnaires and interview inquiries voluntarily. Only 26 employees have replied to the questionnaires, and 24 have participated in the interviews or open-ended inquiries. However, all others expressed interest in responding to the questionnaires. One hundred workers were targeted, but fifty had answered to both closed and open-ended surveys. Questionnaires containing both closed and open-ended questions are utilized to gather data from male and female employees.

The data processing entails editing, coding, tabulating, and analyzing the data with MS Excel and SPSS. Upon concluding the fieldwork, the collected data were meticulously edited, which involved validating and rectifying any inaccuracies to identify potential discrepancies and inconsistencies. Editing must fulfil three criteria: thoroughness, accuracy, and uniformity. Editing was performed to ascertain the accuracy of the acquired information, ensuring that the appropriate sample was interviewed and that three specific questions from the questionnaire were posed, all conducted by me on the day of the interview. The data collected from 50 respondents on various The authors found that among the interviewed tea garden workers, 30% are single and 60% are married, Figure (1).

areas were organized in accordance with requirements. The data was subsequently examined for processing and analysis utilizing various statistical approaches (S.P.S.S. Statistical Package for Social Science) [23]. Various calculations were also articulated in terms of (%), average, and rates. The analytical results and findings have been organized independently, and all works were systematically presented in the format of our study.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Demographic Information

Following Table 01 shows the distribution of the gender of the respondents. The findings show that 30% respondents were in the gender group of Male and 70% respondents were Female.

Table 1: Distribution of the gender of the respondents

Particular	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Male Staff	15	30
Female Staff	35	70
Sub-total	50	100

Source: Authors.

Table 2: Age Category of the respondents.

Age (years)	Frequency	Percentage (%)
18-25	40	80
26-35	6	12
36-45	4	8
46-55	0	0
56 and above	0	0
Total	50	100

Source: Authors.

During the interview, the authors found that 80% respondents are under the age of 18-25, 12% workers under the age of 26-25 years old, Table (2).

Figure 1: Marital Status of Respondents

Source: Authors.

The authors enquire about the satisfaction rate of respondents based on their monthly income level. All respondents indicated their dissatisfaction with their current wage level. From the survey with tea garden workers in the study area, the authors found that 70% respondents have no other source of income while 30% workers said that they have no work to earning, Figure (3).

3.2 Socioeconomic Conditions

Approximately fifty percent of the respondents had finished primary education, 46% were illiterate, and merely 9% had completed secondary education. The literacy rate in the selected study area was 45%, closely aligning with the national average. The selected percentage of homes in the tea garden was 45.00%, closely approximating the national average. The job conditions of the tea garden workers were satisfactory. All household members were found to be engaged in tea labour. Interviewed respondents are daily wage labourers. The authors discovered that 70% of workers earn between BDT 10,000 and 15,000, whereas 30% earn between BDT 5,000 and 10,000 (Fig 2) (1 BDT = 0.0085 USD).

Figure 2: Monthly income of the respondents

Source: Authors.

Figure 3: Percentage of the income options of respondents.

Source: Authors.

Socioeconomic characteristics are quite effective in forecasting the conduct of any population. The specific attributes—such as age, educational attainment, employment history, creditworthiness, and training—are the distinct characteristics that affect group behaviour. An individual's decision-making is influenced by their characteristics. During the study, the authors explored that 90% of tea garden workers are permanent employees, whereas 10% of the daily wage laborers. The working conditions of employees are crucial factors affecting their life and livelihood across all sectors. In the study, the authors found that 60% of respondents indicated that their working conditions are very poor for their occupation, Figure (4).

Figure 4. Housing Condition of Respondents.

Source: Authors.

Housing condition in the tea garden answer this question adequate and well-maintained 0%, adequate but poorly maintained 42% & Inadequate 58% respondents, Table (3).

Table 3. What is the condition of your housing in the tea garden?

Particular	Frequency	(%)
Adequate and well-maintained	0	0
Adequate but poorly maintained	21	42
Inadequate	29	58
Total	50	100

Source: Authors.

As early answer of poor working condition in the tea garden area by the workers, 60% respondents mistreatment and are periodically dismissed from their positions. Respondents said that their basic amenities are absent in the working area where 10% respondents statement are neutral . With following this issue, 34% of the respondents mentioned that their family members faced discrimination at the working area because of religion and caste, Table (4).

Table 4: Respondents about the rate of harassment in the tea garden.

Particular	Frequency	Percentage (%)
Yes	17	34
No	3	6
Not Sure	30	60
Total	50	100

Source: Authors.

The survey and discussions with tea garden workers revealed extensive irregularities and corruption in the Ramgarh tea garden over an extended period. Despite annual directives for housing repairs, no maintenance has occurred for several years. There has been significant carelessness in the medical and communication systems. The ration consistently provides insufficient quantities of rice and red flour, and the quality of the supplied items is notably poor. Furthermore, highways are becoming impracticable for transportation. It has been reported that employees are experiencing

The researchers discovered that an artificial lake has been created, including approximately fifty-two acres of land, alongside the establishment of a fishery project within this lake. The workers were forcibly removed off the site, which was

subsequently utilized for a fishing project and the cultivation of numerous varieties of coconut and betel nut plants. This is entirely outside the regulations of the tea garden. Following the directives of the garden authority, the shade trees valued at lakhs of takas have been unlawfully destroyed, disregarding the prohibitions set forth by the labour leaders. Shade trees and various other species in different portions of the garden have been illicitly harvested for several days; nevertheless, labour leaders have voiced their outrage at the recent sale of six huge trees in sections 3, 24, and 28 of the garden. They also urged the garden authority to cease this unlawful practice.

The Tea Garden authorities initiated the construction of a fishery project featuring a dam on over 150 acres of land near to Bazar Tila Tripura Para. This will diminish the arable land available for agricultural workers. In the event of resistance, the proprietors obstinately announce the unilateral closure of the tea garden without engaging in any dialogue with the workers. Employees are dismissed from their duties. The innocent tea workers are enduring prolonged periods of famine or semi-starvation and confronting uncertainty.

Our interviews with tea garden workers and authorities revealed that processed tea leaves are sold at auction for approximately 220 tk per kg. An average worker can harvest 25 kg of tea leaves. For 25kg of tea leaves, they receive 170 taka. 25 kg of tea leaves can provide 5.5 kg of processed tea leaves, with an auction price of 71, amounting to 1210 tk. Reducing the workers' pay by 170 tk from 1210 tk to 1040 tk signifies that 85.95% of 1210 tk, derived from an individual worker, will be allocated to the owners (the capitalist class).

Tea garden workers in Bangladesh generally receive inadequate compensation, frequently falling short of the government's established minimum wage. Their inadequate wages hinder their ability to fulfil fundamental necessities and maintain a respectable standard of living. Numerous tea plantation proprietors exploit their workers through unjust employment practices. They may neglect to provide appropriate employment contracts or fail to comply with labour regulations concerning working hours, overtime compensation, and perks such as

paid leave. The living conditions in tea garden worker settlements are frequently inadequate. workers frequently reside in congested and deteriorating dwellings with insufficient access to potable water, sanitation services, and healthcare. These circumstances lead to detrimental health and hygiene among the workers and their families. Workers in tea gardens frequently lack access to social security benefits, including healthcare, insurance, and retirement programs. The lack of social safety nets intensifies their vulnerability and hinders their ability to manage emergencies or retire with dignity.

Educational facilities for the offspring of tea garden workers are sometimes insufficient or absent. The absence of access to adequate education sustains a cycle of poverty, constraining opportunities for future generations. Female tea garden workers encounter further obstacles, including gender-based discrimination and harassment. Male colleagues frequently receive more compensation than females for identical work, and females may have obstacles in obtaining healthcare and education.

Certain tea garden proprietors exploit child labour, involving minors in perilous tasks rather than facilitating their access to education. This approach infringes upon children's rights and sustains the cycle of poverty [24, 25]. Numerous tea garden workers encounter obstacles in organizing and establishing labour unions due to insufficient information, harassment from proprietors, and inadequate support. The lack of robust unions impedes workers' ability to jointly champion their rights and negotiate improved working conditions. Tea garden worker sin Bangladesh generally earn insufficient salaries, frequently falling below the government's established minimum wage. These inadequate wages hinder their ability to satisfy fundamental requirements and maintain a respectable standard of living. Numerous tea garden proprietors exploit their workers through unjust employment practices. They may neglect to provide appropriate employment contracts or fail to comply with labour regulations concerning working hours, overtime compensation, and benefits like paid leave. The living conditions in tea garden worker settlements are frequently inadequate. workers frequently reside in congested and deteriorating dwellings with insufficient access to potable water, sanitation services, and medical care. These circumstances lead to detrimental health and hygiene among the workers and their families. Workers in tea gardens frequently lack access to

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Numerous tea garden workers encounter difficulties in organizing and establishing labour unions due to insufficient awareness, harassment from proprietors, and inadequate support. The lack of robust unions impedes workers' ability to jointly assert their rights and negotiate improved working conditions [29, 30].

4. Recommendation

- i. Tea workers receive little formal education; those who are literate possess only elementary-level skills. Their income is anticipated to rise further with the provision of formal schooling.
- ii. They are dissatisfied with the current wage of the tea workers, as the recent salary raise was minimal.
- iii. Many tea workers refrain from undertaking additional labour; nonetheless, if they were to engage in extra labour, their pay would marginally improve, enabling them to better satisfy their demands.
- iv. The aforementioned table and chart indicate that numerous respondents reported experiencing physical illness as a result of working in tea plantations.
- v. The owners of the tea workers organize a list of recreational facilities or cultural activities available in the tea estates.
- vi. (vi) The government should not assume a more proactive role in safeguarding the

socioeconomic welfare of tea plantation workers.

Censuses are executed; nonetheless, tea workers are consistently excluded from enumeration.

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5. Conclusions

The socioeconomic situations of tea garden workers in Bangladesh are marked by numerous obstacles and inequalities within their sociolinguistics context. The workers encounter inadequate remuneration, substandard housing circumstances, restricted access to healthcare and education, and insufficient social protection. These elements perpetuate a cycle of poverty and inequality within the tea garden communities. Marxism posits that capitalist society is founded on inequalities, asserting that every facet of an individual's existence is shaped by economic and social conditions, particularly the class relations that emerge from them, as the meagre wages of workers hinder their ability to satisfy basic needs and support their families. Victor H. Mair and Erling Hough (2009) state in their work, True History of Tea, "For the first time in a popular history of tea, the Chinese, Japanese, Tibetan, and Mongolian annals have been thoroughly consulted."

Numerous individuals reside in confined and inferior accommodations lacking sufficient sanitation amenities. This adversely impacts their physical health and obstructs their capacity to transcend poverty and enhance their living situations.

The restricted availability of healthcare treatments intensifies the difficulties faced by tea garden workers. They frequently lack basic medical facilities, resulting in insufficient healthcare and increased vulnerability to diseases. The lack of adequate education in tea garden regions limits prospects for upward mobility and sustains internationalization poverty. Moreover, the lack of social safety measures renders tea garden workers susceptible to exploitation and unstable working conditions. They experience employment insecurity, endure extended working hours, and frequently operate in perilous settings. The absence of legal protection and representation further diminishes their rights and negotiating ability. Initiatives aimed at enhancing the socioeconomic

conditions of tea garden workers should concentrate on many critical domains. It is essential to ensure fair and sustainable wages that enable employees to meet their basic needs. This can be achieved by instituting more stringent labour standards and ensuring their efficient enforcement. Improving housing quality and providing tea garden workers with access to critical resources such as clean water and sanitation facilities are vital for their overall welfare.

This necessitates expenditures in infrastructure and specialized initiatives designed to enhance living circumstances in tea garden communities. Access to superior healthcare and education is essential for disrupting the cycle of poverty. Efforts must be implemented to enhance healthcare services in tea garden regions and to advance educational possibilities for both children and adults. Marxism posits that economic class struggle can engender significant social transformation, as articulated in its political and social theory. Ultimately, extensive social protection measures must be instituted to furnish tea garden workers with a safety net. This encompasses provisions such as social insurance, health coverage, and legal assistance to safeguard their rights. In conclusion, addressing the socioeconomic challenges encountered by tea garden workers in Bangladesh, within their sociolinguistics framework, requires a holistic approach encompassing equitable remuneration, improved living circumstances, access to healthcare and education, and robust social safety nets. These initiatives are crucial for promoting equality, alleviating poverty, and enabling tea garden workers to live with dignity.

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